

Effective Utilization of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Tools in Management of large class size in Nigerian Universities: Challenges and Way forward

*Shehu, Suleiman Abdullahi Ph.D.¹

Email: shehusuleman78@gmail.com

Tel: 07033674799/08027303904

Bello, Abdulaziz¹

Tel: 08030776713

¹Department of Educational Foundations, Federal University, Gusau PMB-1001, Gusau-Zamfara State

Abstract

The paper examined Effective Utilization of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Tools in Management of large class size in Nigerian Universities: Challenges and Way forward. This is because, the current developments have opened up opportunities for educationists to design and implement Information and Communication Technology (ICT) based lessons especially in tertiary institutions of learning where there are explosion and overcrowding of students. It was based on this premises that, the paper conceptualized ICT Tools in education; Identified the broad objectives of its use and they include: Providing accessibility through online medium of education; Improving the quality of teaching, especially in remote areas and To increase transparency in the education system. Similarly, It Discussed specific ICT Tools for managing large classes in the Nigeria universities' such as: Mobile learning tools; Cloud computing; Individualized learning resources. Highlight and discussed educational advantages of the use of ICT Tools in managing large class which include: Individualization of learning; Online learning & Accessibility to all. Moreso, the paper identified the theoretical framework and explain major challenges affecting the use of ICT Tools in managing large classes and these were: Basic technology infrastructure in Nigerian Universities; Access, Equity and Quality; Training and Technical Support. Furthermore, Conclusion and recommendations on the utilization of ICT tools were enlisted and such recommendations include: Basic technology infrastructure, needed and required for effective use of students and teachers in the university should be ensure and provided

Keywords: ICT; Management; Large Classes, Challenges & Way-forward

Introduction

Educational system around the world has been greatly influenced by the use of materials and tools in teaching and learning from time immemorial, which has been proven in making the process more meaningful, relevant and up to the task. Therefore, the current developments which have opened up opportunities for educationists to design and implement Information and Communication Technology (ICT) based lessons have only poured to the long standing pool of a wider education and technology association existing as bridge which further unified educational course at all levels This bridge between education and computer and internet technology use has made a great impact on perspectives about teaching and learning process especially in tertiary institutions of learning where there are explosion and overcrowding of students commensurate to the broader environmental and societal context. (Ajadi, 2010: Isuku, 2018: Lam, 2021: Marquès,2018). Therefore, advances in Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) have turned the world into a global village and are transforming the world economy presenting challenges that were hitherto un thought of. Nigeria aspires to attain sustainable development and enhance global competitiveness, a status that requires innovations especially in the development of human capital. There is no gainsaying that ICT has become sine qua non in bringing these about. Educators and policy-makers alike agree that ICT is paramount to the future of education and that successful contributions to meeting the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are most likely to be made by ICT in Education initiatives that focus on increasing access through distance learning as ICT can provide new and innovative means to bring educational opportunities to greater numbers of people of all ages, thereby ensuring life-long learning especially for those who over the years have been excluded, such as populations in rural areas, women facing social barriers and people with disabilities. The Federal Ministry of Education is charged with policy formulation, monitoring of implementation, and setting and maintaining standards in the Nigerian education sector. However, the Constitution places education on the Concurrent Legislative List, making education a shared responsibility of the Federal, State and Local Governments. Thus, while the policy and standards with regards to ICT in education are the responsibilities of the Federal

Effective Utilization of Information ... (Shehu & Bello, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10072793>

Government, the implementation of ICT in education rests heavily on the State and Local Governments. ICT occupies a very strategic place in Education in the country. This is encapsulated in the Ministerial Strategy Plan: Education for Change and in series of initiatives and strategies targeted at integrating ICT into education. (Federal Ministry of Education, 2019).

ICT stands for Information and Communication Technology, and it refers to the use of various tools and devices to communicate, create, store, and manage information. It has gained incremental importance for education, employment and communication in recent years. ICTs have become significant tools to access information, educate individuals and conduct interactive instructional activities regardless of time and location (Ajadi, 2010; Isuku, 2018; Lam, 2021; Marquès, 2018). Similarly, Information and Communications Technology, as the name suggests are tools that handle information and produce, store, and disseminate information. ICT comprises of both old and new tools. Old tools include radio, TV, Telephone. New tools comprise computers, satellites, the Internet, and wireless technology. It exists in multiple forms like audio, video, audio-visual, and texts. It refers to the latest technologies and a repository of simple audio-visual aids such as slides, radio, cassette, and film. ICT is defined as “A diverse set of technologies, tools, and resources used to communicate, create, disseminate, store, and manage information.” These technologies include computers, the internet, radio and TV. (Mannreet, 2021).

Scholars asserted that ‘Information and Communication Technology’ (ICT) needs not be overemphasized because it first appeared in the mid-1980s to represent an umbrella term for all kinds of electronic systems used for broadcasting telecommunications and mediated communications in its popular use then and this included personal computers, video games, cell phones, internet, and electronic mediation and payment systems etc. The main justification advanced as the reason for the emergence of the term in such a compound form was the fact that the computer technology is regarded as the tool for storing, processing and retrieving information in electronic form whereas the communication technology facilitates transmission of that information from source device (usually regarded as client) to destination device (usually regarded as server). This simultaneity of function made the component words inseparable in usage ever since. Other scholars simply considered ICT as combination of computing and networking technology with the dual function of information processing provided by the former and information transmission carried out by the latter. Thus, ICT came to mean the generality of tools used for gathering, processing, storing and disseminating of Information. The invention of the internet and its liberalization at the turn of the century led to 2.0 and 3.0 generations of the ICT which can be appreciated in the fullest in the Education realm. (Haugsbakk & Nordkvelle 2017).

Although, the developments in 3.0 generations of ICT included machine learning and other aspects of augmented reality that embody complex interactions of learner and technology to the point of relegating the human teacher, the ICT in the education system is still largely regarded as arbiter of educational interactions. In a one of the study conducted following Covid-19 pandemic, stressed ICT usage as arbiter of educational interactions as the dominant trend. ICT usage in educational institutions has undergone a significant evolution from its inception to the present time, moving from simply facilitating administrative tasks to being an important aid for class management and integral part of the learning process itself, the desired outcomes on students' performance cannot be delivered by the ICT automatically. The bizzare of ICT may be considered as comprises the computer hardware, software, application of telecommunication technologies, projection devices, Local Area Network (LAN), Wide Area Network (WAN), digital cameras, Compact Disks (CDs), Digital Video Disks (DVDs), cell phones, satellites, and fiber optics among others (Affouneh, Salha & Khlaif, 2020).

Following this trend, it is important to note that, the demand for university education in particular is usually tracked through official gateways to educational institutions of respective countries. In Nigeria the data from the joint admissions and matriculations board (JAMB) provides enough proof to support these assertions. A study conducted by Isuku (2018) which reported patterns of admission applications into tertiary institutions and the rate of admissions offered indicates a consistent trend of gross imbalance between the figures of admissions sought and admissions granted. According to the data the highest percentage of admissions offers then was 33%. This wide gap gave a recipe for utilization of the potential of the ICTs to attend to educational needs of the large swaths of the unadmitted as well as the admitted who are also in unmanageably large numbers. In a paper on Private Universities in Nigeria—the Challenges Ahead, Ajadi (2010) suggests that the vivid inability of governments' institutions to accommodate the rising demand for education necessitated the establishment of additional universities in the past few years. This scenario was what led to argue that the zeal for providing education as a social service in Nigeria has not been matched with a zeal for funding it. These prospects made the ICTs significant path and to an extent a means to penetrate all aspects of educational pursuit providing newer and more efficient means of teaching, learning and educational administration. That, the resulting ICT integration phenomenon served to strengthen the government's regulatory and institutional framework of the educational system rather than educational delivery to the public. Consequently, it became clear that no education system can afford to ignore the issue of developing an appropriate ICT-in-education policy and

Effective Utilization of Information ... (Shehu & Bello, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10072793>

implementation strategies at a national system level keeping in mind its diverse prospects and challenges. This is because, it covered wide areas encompassing distance education and the facilitation of teaching methods and delivery in conventional educational institutions. Within these conventional institutions, one of the biggest problems believed to be addressed by proper Instructional ICT integration is the problem of large classes and over crowdedness (Ajadi, 2010: Isuku, 2018: Lam, 2021: Marquès, 2018)

The term large class is context-dependent which implies that its usage differs from one environmental or cultural circumstance to another. However, Large class environments are not new to students and teachers in Nigeria's tertiary educational institutions, the phenomenon is commonly believed to pose significant challenges for the teaching-learning process. Such challenges include coping with inadequate space and equipment, classroom management problems, poor quality of teaching, difficulty in marking students' tests and examination scripts, poor teacher-student interactions, teachers' stress due to heavy workload, and inability of teachers to adequately meet the learning needs of individual learners. So it has been envisaged that, the application of ICT and Virtual Learning Environment (VLE), will not only improve and enhance the relationships between teachers and students but undergone a phenomenal change, of the role of the teachers, the nature and context of learning as well as the function and relative importance of the contents of courses all will be challenged and redefined with the use of information and communication

Conceptualization of the term ICT tools in Nigerian Universities:

ICT stands for Information and Communication Technology, and it refers to the use of various tools and devices to communicate, create, store, and manage information. More so, it can be seen as tools that handle information and produce, store, and disseminate information. ICT comprises of both old and new tools. Old tools include radio, TV, Telephone. New tools comprise computers, satellites, the Internet, and wireless technology. It exists in multiple forms like audio, video, audio-visual, and texts. It refers to the latest technologies and a repository of simple audio-visual aids such as slides, radio, cassette, and film. ICT is defined as a diverse set of technologies, tools, and resources used to communicate, create, disseminate, store, and manage information." These technologies include computers, the internet, radio and TV. There are three ways by which ICT can be considered as an important tool in education. These are as follows: (Mannreet, 2021),

1. **ICT education:** ICT education means using trained personnel who can meet the needs and deliver information effectively to society. The vision is to train people and to equip students with ICT skills and knowledge.
2. **ICT-supported education:** It is also known as multimedia education. Around the world, many institutes and universities use ICT tools for printed study materials. It includes broadcast media, like radio, TV, audio-visual aids among others
3. **ICT-enabled education:** ICT-enabled education means the content is disseminated through ICT tools. Here, ICT is considered as a medium required for the teaching-learning process. (Mannreet, 2021)

Before now it has been established that, the central role of ICT in effective teaching and learning has made its adoption imperative for teachers in teaching situations as a result of an increase in the student population. However, Eze and Aja, (2014) further buttress that knowledge explosion has brought a lot of development to learning through myriads of media which has led to an upgrade of human knowledge in the 21st Century. The role of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) in sustaining education cannot be overstated due to its importance in both teaching and learning. Effective integration of ICT plays an important role in improving the quality of instruction delivery within and outside the classroom. Yusuf (2015) posited that no country can claim to be educationally advanced unless it embraces technology for its educational activities. ICT as tools within the school environment include use for school administration and management; teaching and learning of ICT related skills to enhance class work presentation; teaching/learning repetitive tasks; teaching/learning intellectual thinking and problem solving skills; stimulating creativity and imagination; for research by teachers and students, and as communication tool by teachers and students (Alshmrany & Wilkinson, 2017: Amuchie, 2015: Basargekar, & Singhavi, 2017: and Olawale, et al: 2020)

Broad objectives of the use of ICT Tools in Nigeria Universities:

The following are the objectives and rationales for the use of ICT tools in university system of education as identified by (Mannreet, 2021)

1. Providing accessibility through online medium of education.
2. Improving the quality of teaching, especially in remote areas.
3. To increase transparency in the education system.
4. To strengthen the policies, rules, and laws in the education system.

Effective Utilization of Information ... (Shehu & Bello, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10072793>

5. To analyze the learning and participation of the students and measure its effectiveness.
6. Measuring and evaluating students' behavior, involvement, and retention in the learning process.
7. To analyze students' performance, placement, and application of knowledge. (Mannreet, 2021)

Specific ICT Tools that can be used for managing large class in Nigeria Universities;

ICT Tools that can be used in teaching and learning are broadly divided into hardware, software, and network communication. The tools are suitable for students and teachers. This is because, over the time ICT has become integral to the teaching-learning interaction, sometimes through such approaches as replacing chalkboards with interactive digital whiteboards, using students' own or schools' devices for learning during class time, and e-learning models where students learn at home or workplace. these approaches can lead to higher order thinking skills, provide creative and individualized avenues for students to learn and express their understanding. A plethora of groupings of these tools and resources have been proposed by different scholars. Some of the commonest among them as identified by scholars (Ajadi, 2010: Isuku, 2018: Lam, 2021: Marquès, 2018)

Mobile Learning tools in Nigerian Universities;

New advances in hardware and software are making handheld "smartphones" indispensable tools for present day learning. High levels of digital penetration in countries enabled adoption of mobile learning tools as suitable learning devices. According to Nigerian National Communications Commission, NCC as at June 2022, the Nigerian Digital penetration stands at 44.3% predominantly represented by internet enabled mobile devices (Vanguard, 2022). This figure establishes high potential for ICT Educational integration in the country

Cloud computing in Nigerian Universities;

Applications are increasingly moving off of the standalone desktop computer and increasingly onto server farms accessible through the Internet largely hosted in cloud. Educational systems take advantage of this trend to further their course. Given the fact that connectivity provided by cloud computing resources have relative immunity from natural disasters made its adoption more ubiquitous and popular in education system.

Individualized learning resources in Nigerian Universities;

This is often referred to as personalized or customized learning, the application of individualized methods of learning in education predates the current association of education and ICT. However, the trend even in physical classrooms around the world today provides an information appliance to average and special learners with varying learning abilities. It creates learning environments and adopt tools that assume universal access to the learning. These tools not only helped in achieving smaller class sizes and mitigation of negative effects of poor student-teacher interactions but also facilitated customization of learning to individual learners' needs and characteristics (Bello, 2021: Lam, Tse, Lu & Wong 2021).

Ubiquitous learning tools in Nigeria Universities;

Appearance of increasingly robust connectivity infrastructure particularly in the area of open source Technology largely accessed freely or at subsidized cost make it possible for learners to study "anytime" and "anywhere". Here also the global Covid-19 pandemic has exerted considerable influence on its emergence. Research shows that in its wake different countries in the world often in collaboration with international partners helped made a significant addition to the ubiquitous ICT tools for learning purposes. at both lower and higher institution levels (Reyes-Chua, Sibbaluca, Miranda, Palmario, Moreno & Solon 2020). In Nigeria also, the federal ministry of education launched a robust e-learning facility that students and teachers can access freely (Nigerian Tribune, 2021). Even though ubiquitous learning tools have been critiqued by researchers for paucity of direct student teacher interactions, the availability of virtual mentors or teachers and affordances of peer to peer and self-paced learning make it advantageous (Yeung, Carpenter & Corral 2021).

Virtual teaching platforms in Nigerian Universities;

Another well-known tool in the educational field for the great amount of benefits it provides to students and to maintained large classes are the virtual teaching platforms, it is understood as that tool which allows the student to study the subject (Curriculum content) at a distance without the need to travel to the classroom/ lecture venue and or training center. This has the advantage to allowed for different modalities of study such as e-learning or e-learning in Spanish or b-learning or blended learning. (Yeung, Carpenter & Corral 2021).

Effective Utilization of Information ... (Shehu & Bello, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10072793>

Educational advantages of the use of ICT Tools in managing large class in Nigeria Universities;

The use of ICT technology in teaching and learning is expanding rapidly in this twenty-first century. As a result of that, studies about the importance of ICT technology in teaching and learning are also appearing in a growing number. Previous research shows that the use of technologies, particularly the new ones could facilitate communication, reduce anxiety, encourage oral discussion, develop the writing/thinking connection, nurture social or cooperative learning among others. But more specifically, the below were enumerated as educational advantages of the use of ICT Tools in teaching and that could help manage large classes as postulated by (Vinay.2021)

Individualization of learning in Nigerian Universities: It is an established fact that, no two individual student learn within the same rate, this is for the individual differences in existence, hence, it means that people learn as an individual and not as the same group. As learners are varied, ICTs provide flexibility so that learners learn according to their own pace and this check the problem around most learn at the same pace and time

Online learning in Nigerian Universities: ICT and its tools had led to the emergence of online learning. Through this, the teachers and the students are learning innovative ways in the education process. Online learning has gained popularity amidst the corona pandemic to ensure that the learning continues. ICTs have looked after that education reaches through it worldwide and even in remote areas. No matter where the students are, but it has ensured that every learner derives its benefits.

Accessible to all in Nigerian Universities: ICT in education allows accessibility to all types of learners. All students can learn through the material provided. Even the special needs students can maximize the benefits through the usage of it. ICT has also covered issues like the “digital divide” and allows even less fortunate people to access the tools for their educational needs and enhance learning.

Higher-order thinking & skill developments in Nigerian Universities: ICT promotes high order thinking and reasoning skills. These skills enabled the process of evaluation, planning, monitoring, controlling, reflecting, etc. To use ICT tools effectively, one must be able to explain and justify the solutions to the problems. For using ICTs, the students should be able to discuss, test, and evaluate the strategies and methods they use.

Better subject learning in Nigerian Universities: The key role of ICT is to enhance subject learning and acquire skills. It promotes key learning in areas of literacy and numeracy.

Develops ICT literacy and capability in Nigerian Universities: Literacy and capability are the 21st-century skills that are needed. One of the best ways to develop these is to equip the subject-matter with purposeful activities.

Encourages collaboration in Nigerian Universities: ICT fosters collaboration as children work collectively. It also enhances communication skills as they discuss, talk, and learn together. All you need is a laptop, tablet, or desktop computer to understand it's working. ICT tools open up the doors for developing language through fostering communication.

Motivates learning in Nigerian Universities: ICT motivates children towards learning. Children learn better through the usage of technology. They get mesmerized with technology tools and get motivated to learn effectively in the classroom or at home.

Improves engagement and knowledge retention in Nigerian Universities: With the inclusion of ICT in education and its tools, students get more engaged and show greater participation in learning. It is all because of technology. It has made learning fun-filled with creativity and games. It enhances learning in multiple ways. Because of it, the students learn better, leading to knowledge retention.

Effective differentiation instruction with ICT technology in Nigerian Universities: There are varied learners with distinct learning styles in this society. So, technology does the task of providing differentiated instruction to different learners.

A key part of the curriculum in Nigerian Universities: As per the latest curriculum, ICT plays an important part in the education system. So, many governments across the globe have started using ICT as a major part of education and the curriculum. (Vinay.2021)

Challenges around the use of ICT Tools in managing large classes in Nigerian Universities

There are some identified challenges militating against the effective use of ICT tools and resources to curtail challenges of large classes facing university educational provisions in Nigeria. These challenges were grouped by scholars having relationship with the major three ones of the following: (Johnson, Jacovina, Russell & Soto 2016): Access, Equity and Quality. While from the above, they deduced the following generic challenges which can include the following:

1. Basic technology infrastructure in Nigerian Universities;

Governments all over the world shoulder the responsibility for installing technology basic infrastructure such as electricity and internet connectivity. However, increased affordability and flexibility of ICT within a short span made it possible to be large

Effective Utilization of Information ... (Shehu & Bello, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10072793>

swaths of the teachers/lecturers and other members of the population to acquire internet enabled device with or without Institutional direct support. (Johnson, Jacovina, Russell & Soto 2016).

2. Hardware in Nigerian Universities;

No matter the robustness of the internet connectivity and software, access to hardware by the end user remains critical. Early accounts of technology integration focused much of their interest on increasing the availability of computers in schools. But with the later developments the focus has relatively shifted toward content and software development. In the Nigerian case access to mobile devices come mostly by personal funding. However for effective technology integration to be achieved to avert the negative consequences of large classes, access to official equipment necessary must be increased. In a number of developed countries, 1-1 lecturer computer ratio by official provision or facilitation has since been achieved. In addition, the official computer/device possession by lecturers averts the problems of none-regularity and non-dependability of hardware (Johnson, Jacovina, Russell & Soto 2016).

3. Software in Nigerian Universities;

Educational institutions have since been keeping large reservoir of knowledge in print form in libraries. The surge in ICT made them to put their academic resources and services online, bringing the global community onto a common platform and awakening the interest of stakeholders. Despite continuing technical challenges, online education shows great potential. The popularity of open source software yet offers flexible and affordable approach to addressing the technical problems in providing optimal delivery of online learning. Open source refers to both the concept and practice of making program and content source openly available. Development of wikis made users and to have access to the core designing functionalities that enable them to modify or add features to the source code for redistribution. It is stressed extensive collaboration and circulation are central to the open source movement (Johnson, Jacovina, Russell & Soto 2016).

4. Training in Nigerian Universities;

Mostly, cited reason for lack of technology implementation in the classroom for effective management of large classes is inadequate professional development and training. Therefore, with relevant training on technology adoption and use teachers/lecturers will show increasing confidence in technology integration to mitigate Negative effect of large classes. But given that technology is constantly changing, it is more important than ever that lecturers of higher Institutions stay up-to-date with their technological expertise and pedagogical expertise. professional development and training to break through the challenges (Johnson, Jacovina, Russell & Soto 2016).

5. Technical support in Nigerian Universities;

In cases where the professional training of lecturers do not enable them to use Technology for proper management of large classes, technical support must be sought and be provided appropriately (Johnson, Jacovina, Russell & Soto 2016).

6. Curriculum:

There is generally lack of regular review and updating of existing ICT curricula, especially at the tertiary level, to meet changing societal needs. There is also low capacity of curriculum developers and implementers. The challenge of outdated curriculum is even more pronounced in view of the dynamic nature of ICT Tools

7. Funding in Nigerian Universities:

Although, funds are being provided for ICT in education, they are largely inadequate to provide the drive necessary to position the sector for the attainment of the national goals. The foregoing reveals that the state of ICT in education in Nigeria falls below global standards. This reinforces the need for focused intervention in ICT in education.

Use of ICT for effective classroom instruction in Nigerian Universities

ICT Tools plays a significant role towards creating an improved teaching and learning environment is of utmost importance to teachers in creating a new learning culture. Many teachers lack the knowledge and skills to effectively use ICT tools in facilitating learning in increasingly ICT-pervasive learning environments. Some teacher-training programme have over-emphasized computer literacy while not enabling teachers to integrate technology with pedagogy and facilitate ICT-assisted interactive teaching-learning at classroom level, therefore, a theoretical framework is a conceptual model of how one theorizes makes logical sense of the relationship among the several factors that have been identified as important to the problem. A framework is a representation of reality; it delineates those aspects (variables) of the real world the scientist considers to be relevant to the problem The figure 1 & 2 below depicts the interrelationships of the necessary organs surrounding the use of ICT Tools for teaching and learning and as well an interrelated variables that would bring about its effective integration and use in tertiary institution of learning.

Effective Utilization of Information ... (Shehu & Bello, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10072793>

Conclusion

Implementing ICT for management of large classes is both challenging and a rewarding endeavor this is because, The notable increase in the social use of ICTs and their enormous impact is an aspect that cannot go unnoticed in the world of education. ICT is already becoming a fundamental tool for new teachers and students in the classroom. It has been proven that the use of ICT in the classroom increases the motivation of the students, showing more interest and becoming more involved in the areas they study. ICT enables the use of innovative educational resources and the renewal of learning methods, establishing a more active collaboration of students and the simultaneous acquisition of technological knowledge. Therefore, Schools use a diverse set of ICT tools to communicate, create, disseminate, store, and manage information. In some contexts, ICT has also become integral to the teaching-learning interaction, through such approaches as replacing chalkboards with interactive digital whiteboards, using students' own smartphones or other devices for learning during class time, and the "flipped classroom" model where students watch lectures at home on the computer and use classroom time for more interactive exercises. When teachers are digitally literate and trained to use ICT, these approaches can lead to higher order thinking skills, provide creative and individualized options for students to express their understandings, and leave students better prepared to deal with ongoing technological change in society and the workplace thereby ensuring learning at university system turn to be any-where and any-time, any place a phenomenon that will bring about learning management and help checkmate challenges of overcrowding

Recommendations

The following recommendations if implemented will go a long way to improve on the use of ICT in the management of large class in Nigeria University System

1. Basic technology infrastructure, needed and required for effective use and functionality of students and teachers should ensure are in place, such to include high bandwidth connectivity of online and internet services within and around the campus should be intensify
2. Hardware components suitable for functioning alongside with the software should be made available and adequate for students' and teachers uses
3. Training Series of on the job and induction training for staff on the uses of ICT tools should be prioritized and University system should ensure time to time training of teachers in order to updates knowledge and skills
4. Tactical support is required from the government for maximizing productivity

Acknowledgement

Gratitude to my colleagues who provided constructive criticism and inputs to this piece of article.

References

- Alshmrany, S & Wilkinson, B. (2017). Factors influencing the adoption of ICT by teachers in primary schools in Saudi Arabia teachers' perspectives of the integration of ICT in primary education. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, vol. 8, no.12, pp. 1-14.
- Amuchie, A. A. (2015). Availability and utilization of ICT resources in teaching and learning in secondary schools in Ardo-Kola and Jalingo, Taraba State. *Journal of Poverty, Investment and Development*, vol. 8, pp. 94-100.
- Basargekar, P. & Singhavi, C. (2017). Factors affecting teachers' perceived proficiency in using ICT in the classroom. *IAFOR Journal of Education*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 67-84.
- Agabi, C. O. (2010). Prudential approach to resource management in Nigerian education: A theoretical perspective. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Education*, 3(2), 94-106.
- Ajadi, T. O. (2010). Private Universities in Nigeria—the Challenges Ahead. *Private Universities in Nigeria—the Challenges Ahead.*, 1(7), 1-10.
- Akpan, C. P. (2014). ICT competence and lecturers' job efficacy in universities in Cross River State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 4(10), 259-266.
- Amaghous, J., & Zouine, M. (2022). A Critical Analysis of the Governance of the Moroccan Education System in the Era of Online Education. In *Socioeconomic Inclusion During an Era of Online Education* (pp. 156-176). IGI Global.
- Bagchi, K., & Udo, G. (2007). Empirically testing factors that drive ICT adoption in Africa and OECD set of nations. *Issues in information systems*, 8(2), 45-52.

Effective Utilization of Information ... (Shehu & Bello, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10072793>

- Bello, B. (2021). students 'disengagement And E-Learning: Adaptivity As Key Challenge For Post-COVID 19 E-Learning Systems In Nigeria. *Sokoto Educational Review*, 20(1&2), 30-39.
- Collins, A., & Halverson, R. (2010). The second educational revolution: Rethinking education in the age of technology. *Journal of computer assisted learning*, 26(1), 18-27
- Olawale, et al: (2020) Assessment of Teachers' Pedagogical Knowledge on the Utilization of Information and Communication Technology in Kwara State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Development using Information and Communication Technology (IJEDICT)*, 2020, Vol. 16, Issue 1, pp. 62-71
- Eze, P. I. & Aja, S. N. (2014). Availability and utilization of information and communication technology (ICT) in Ebonyi Local Government area of Ebonyi state: implications for effective teaching and learning. *Educational Research*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 116-121.
- Ekundayo, M. S., & Ekundayo, J. M. (2009). Capacity constraints in developing countries: A need for more e-learning space? The case of Nigeria. *Proceeding ascilite Auckland*.
- (Federal Ministry of Education, 2019) National Policy On Information And Communication Technologies (Ict) In Education
- Haugsbakk, G., & Nordkvelle, Y. (2007). The rhetoric of ICT and the new language of learning: A critical analysis of the use of ICT in the curricular field. *European educational research journal*, 6(1), 1-12.
- Isuku, E. J. (2018). Challenges and prospects of ICT facilities in improving access to the open distance learning programme of African universities: Research evidence from Nigeria. *US-China Education Review A*, 8(6), 259-266.
- Johnson, A. M., Jacovina, M. E., Russell, D. G., & Soto, C. M. (2016). Challenges and solutions when using technologies in the classroom. In *Adaptive educational technologies for literacy instruction* (pp. 13-30). Routledge.
- Lam, P. L., Ng, H. K., Tse, A. H., Lu, M., & Wong, B. Y. (2021). eLearning technology and the advancement of practical constructivist pedagogies: Illustrations from classroom observations. *Education and Information Technologies*, 26(1), 89-101.
- Lembani, R., Gunter, A., Breines, M., & Dalu, M. T. B. (2020). The same course, different access: the digital divide between urban and rural distance education students in South Africa. *Journal of Geography in Higher Education*, 44(1), 70-84.
- Mannreet, K., (2021), What is ICT in Education and Its Importance, Jan 4, 2021 / [Interactive Education](#)
- Marquès, P. (2018). The digital board.Recovery from [http:// www. Peremarchs. Net /](http://www.Peremarchs.Net/)
- Manenji, T., & Marufu, B. (2016). The impact of adopting e-government as a mechanism to enhance accountability as well as transparent conduct within public institutions. *Scholedge International Journal of Business Policy & Governance*, 3(7), 84-101.
- Ndethiu, S. M., Masingila, J. O., Miheso-O'Connor, M. K., Khatete, D. W., & Heath, K. L. (2017). Kenyan secondary teachers' and principals' perspectives and strategies on teaching and learning with large classes. *Africa Education Review*, 14(1), 58-86.
- Ponelis, S. R., & Holmner, M. A. (2015). ICT in Africa: Building a better life for all. *Information Technology for Development*, 21(2), 163-177.
- Reyes-Chua, E., Sibbaluca, B. G., Miranda, R. D., Palmario, G. B., Moreno, R. P., & Solon, J. P. T. (2020). The status of the implementation of the e-learning classroom in selected higher education institutions in region IV-A amidst the COVID-19 crisis. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(11), 253-258.
- Rodríguez-Abitia, G., & Kriscautzky-Laxague, M. (2018). A Framework for ICT Usage Classification of Higher Education Institutions.
- Vorster, J., & Goosen, L. (2017). A framework for university partnerships promoting continued support of e-schools. In *Proceedings of the 46th Annual Conference of the Southern African Computer Lecturers' Association (SACLA 2017)*, Magaliesburg.
- Yeung, K. L., Carpenter, S. K., & Corral, D. (2021). A comprehensive review of educational technology on objective learning outcomes in academic contexts. *Educational psychology review*, 33(4), 1583-1630.